

**Macroeconomic Variables and Industrial Goods Sector Index Performance:
Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX)**

Ibrahim Kukandaka,¹ Abdullahi Musa Abdullahi PhD.,² & Salihu Liman Mairafi, PhD.³

¹Corresponding author. Email: kukandaka3527@yahoo.com

²Department of Taxation, Nasarawa State University (NSUK), Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Email: aamusa@nsuk.edu.ng

³Email: mairafisalihu@nsuk.edu.ng

¹ & ³ Department of Banking and Finance, Faculty of Administration, Nasarawa State University (NSUK), Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Abstract:

This study examines the effect of exchange rate, interest rate, and inflation on the Industrial Goods Sector Index of the Nigerian Exchange Group, addressing the limited sector-specific evidence in existing literature. An ex post facto research design is adopted using monthly secondary data from 2012 to 2025 sourced from the Nigerian Exchange Group and the National Bureau of Statistics. The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) is employed to analyze both short-run dynamics and long-run relationships. The findings confirm a significant long-run cointegrating relationship between macroeconomic variables and the Industrial Goods Sector Index. Inflation has a positive and statistically significant long-run effect, while exchange rate and interest rate are insignificant in both the short and long run. The error correction term indicates a strong adjustment process, correcting about 61% of disequilibrium monthly. The study concludes that inflation is the dominant driver of industrial sector performance in Nigeria. Therefore, policymakers should prioritize inflation control to ensure sector stability. Investors should focus on inflation trends and adopt long-term strategies, while firms should implement measures to hedge against inflationary pressures.

Keywords: NGX, Industrial Goods Index, Exchange-Rate, Inflation-Rate, Interest-Rate.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Serving as both a platform for investment and a gauge for the economy, the stock market holds significant importance for firms, investors, policymakers, and regulators. It enables investors to generate returns from surplus funds, which in turn supports corporate growth. For policymakers and analysts, its value lies in providing real-time indicators of broader economic and financial health (Ross, 1976). Stock market performance is typically assessed through indices that track price movements of constituent securities, thereby indicating whether market conditions are bullish or bearish. Globally, benchmarks such as the S&P 500, Dow Jones Industrial Average, FTSE 100, Nikkei 225, and CSI 300 guide investment decisions and policy evaluations, reflecting collective market reactions to domestic and global developments (Guha et al., 2016).

In Nigeria, the Nigerian Exchange (formerly Nigerian Stock Exchange) launched its first All-Share Index (ASI) in 1984 with an initial value of 100 points. Since then, it has crossed major thresholds: 1,000 points in 1992, 10,000 points in 2000, and stood at 155,613.03 points by December 2025 (NGX Fact Sheet, 2026). To enhance transparency and enable sector-specific analysis, the NGX introduced several sector-specific indices such as the NGX 30, Banking, Insurance, Consumer Goods, Industrial Goods, Oil & Gas, Pension, and Lotus Islamic indices (Ikoku & Okorie, 2010). These indices provide insights into how distinct groups of firms respond to macroeconomic conditions. For instance, the Banking Index captures financial sector dynamics, the Consumer Goods Index reflects food and beverage producers, while the Industrial Goods Index tracks heavy manufacturing and cement firms.

Sectorial indices serve as important analytical tools for understanding how related firms react to fluctuations in macroeconomic variables. Factors such as inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, GDP growth, and global oil prices influence investor behavior and sector profitability in varying ways (Chauhan et al., 2025). Empirical evidence shows that stock markets are sensitive to macroeconomic shifts (Celebi & Hönig, 2019; Asamoah et al., 2019; Mbulawa, 2015), although the effects often differ across industries (Baker et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2017). While macroeconomic variables are widely recognized to influence stock market performance, sector-specific effects, especially within the Industrial Goods sector which is highly vulnerable to exchange rate depreciation and inflation due to its dependence on imported machinery and raw materials remain insufficiently explored.

A clear example of such sector-specific impacts occurred following the Central Bank Nigeria (CBN) floatation of the naira in mid-2023, intended to unify multiple exchange rates, the currency weakened by 96% by the end of 2024, inflation soared past 33% by November 2024, prompting the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to raise the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) from 17% to 27.5% (Bloomberg 2024, NBS December 2024). The action created stark contrasts across sectors: banks realized substantial FX revaluation gains, whereas Industrial Goods firms recorded an estimated ₦1.7 trillion in FX losses, diminishing profitability and investor confidence. This sensitivity was reflected in market performance, with the Industrial Goods Index falling by 0.04% in June 2024, compared to gains of 2.5% and 1.4% in the Banking and Insurance indices, respectively. Such divergence underscores the Nigerian market's heterogeneity and the varied sensitivities of sectors to macroeconomic shocks (Abdullahi, 2020).

Despite these clear sector-level dynamics, most Nigerian studies, such as Akanbi (2025), Ojikutu et al (2017), Fernando (2017), Okere et al (2021) and Ejem (2020), focus

on the broader market, particularly the All-Share Index, and overlook how macroeconomic variables uniquely influence specific sectors such as Industrial Goods. Consequently, this study examines the impact of exchange rate, inflation, and interest rate on the sectoral indices of the Nigerian stock market, with special emphasis on the NGX Industrial Goods Index. The objective is to provide a deeper understanding of macro-financial transmission mechanisms within the industrial sector and support evidence-based decision-making among policymakers, investors, and market analysts. In line with the above, this study determines the relationship between exchange rate, interest rate inflation rate and industrial goods sector index of the Nigeria stock market.

2. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

2.1 Exchange rate and industrial good sector index

Mudiangombe et al (2022) investigated whether currency risk is priced differently in the different sectors (industrial, financial, and basic materials) of equity markets in a sample of developed United States of America (USA) and developing economies (Brazil, India, Poland, and South Africa). The paper makes use of Univariate Autoregressive Fractionally Integrated Moving Average and Exponential General Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedastic (ARFIMA-EGARCH), the Markov Switching method (MS), and the Canonical Vine Copulas (C-Vine) techniques. Using a sample of daily data made of the foreign exchange rate against the domestic currency and equity market sectors and found that there is an asymmetry effect between equity markets and the foreign exchange rate: there is a heterogeneous, strong, and positive dependence between the two.

Fasanya and Akinwale (2022) examined the effect of exchange rate shocks on ten (10) sectorial stock returns in Nigeria from January 2007 to December 2018. The autoregressive distributed lag and nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag are employed to examine symmetric and asymmetric relationship between exchange rate and sectorial stock returns. The result showed that only financial service sector moves in an asymmetric fashion in the short and long period without taking account of structural breaks and with structural breaks, none of the sectorial stock returns were asymmetric. The result shows that exchange rate movement affects the sectors differently.

Banda (2017) analyzed long- and short-run causal relationships between South Africa's Industrial Index 25 and key macroeconomic variables particularly exchange rate using quarterly data from 1995Q3 to 2015Q2 within a VECM and Granger causality framework. Findings showed that inflation positively affects stock prices, interest rates negatively influence the index, and exchange rates have a positive impact, while GDP shows no significant relationship. The VECM produced two error-correction terms: one insignificant, and one significant, indicating short-term adjustments and a long-run relationship from GDP, inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates to the INDI25. Granger causality results revealed only a one-way causality from the INDI25 to prime rates.

Pyeman and Ahmad (2017) examined how sectoral indices in the Malaysian stock market relate to exchange rates from 1995 to 2014. After confirming stationarity at first difference, Johansen cointegration and VECM results showed long-run linkages between macroeconomic variables and sectoral indices, particularly in the Technology sector. VAR analysis further revealed short-run relationships for several sectors, including Financials, Industrials, Consumer Products, Industrial Products, Properties, and Trade & Services.

Kotha and Sahu (2016) examined long and short run relations between Exchange Rate and other selected macroeconomic indicators and stock market returns with reference to India. The study employed monthly data from July 2001 to July 2015 since major stock market reforms viz., ban of Badla system, introduction of rolling settlement and introduction of stock derivatives, were all implemented in July 2001. With the help of co-integration and error correction model, the study revealed the presence of long run relation between the BSE Sensex and select macroeconomic indicators viz., Exchange Rate, Wholesale Price Index, T-bill rates and M3.

2.2 Inflation and industrial goods sector index

Suriani et al. (2024) analyzed how inflation affected Indonesia's sectorial stock markets Consumer Goods (CGI), Basic Industry and Chemical (BIC), and Miscellaneous Industry (MSI) before and during COVID-19, using monthly data from 2008–2020 and VAR-based techniques. They found that shocks within each sector negatively influenced future stock performance. The CGI sector positively influenced the Rupiah exchange rate, while the MSI sector was adversely affected by inflation, with inflation fluctuations closely linked to MSI movements. Exchange rate changes also affected both MSI and CGI. A one-way causality existed for the CGI and BIC sectors. Overall, all three sectors showed positive responses to disturbances in inflation and exchange rates.

Amadi et al (2022) investigated the effect of time varying inflation on the Iranian stock market industry index using conditional regression (WLS-Rolling Window) with monthly data during the period from April 2018 to March 2018. Conditional regression results show that the effect of inflation on the industry index is not constant over time, in the sense that inflation has had a positive effect on the industry index at some times and a negative effect on the industry index at some times. In addition, this effect has had a drastic change since August 2019, when the trend of the industry index has changed.

Herlando and Sishadiyati (2022) analyzed the effects of inflation and exchange rates on sectorial stock prices on the Indonesia Stock Exchange using monthly data from 2018–2020 and multiple regression analysis. They found that inflation significantly influenced most sectorial indices, except the Basic Industry, Financial, and Trade sectors. Exchange rates also affected most indices, except Mining and Trade. Overall, inflation was the dominant factor across eight sectorial indices, while the remaining sectors were more influenced by exchange rate movements.

Erer (2021) examined the impact of inflation and inflation uncertainty on the BIST 100 and its sectorial indices from 2004–2021 using EGARCH and NARDL models. The study confirmed long-run cointegration between stock returns, inflation, and inflation uncertainty. Inflation shocks had no significant effect on the BIST 100, services, energy, or telecom sectors but significantly and negatively affected the materials and technology sectors in both the short and long run. Negative inflation shocks also reduced returns in the financial, banking, industrial, and IT sectors, especially in the short term.

Jefry and Djazuli (2020) analyzed the impact of inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates on stocks of basic industrial and chemical manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2013 to 2017 using OLS. The study found that, jointly, the three macroeconomic variables significantly affected stock performance. Individually, inflation had a significant effect on stock returns, while interest rates and exchange rates showed no significant impact on stocks in the basic industry and chemical sector.

Yogaswari et al. (2012) investigated how inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates influence stock prices on the Indonesia Stock Exchange using monthly data from 2007 to 2011. Using multiple regression, they found significant relationships between these macroeconomic variables and stock prices in the Jakarta Composite Index, the agriculture sector, and the basic industry sector. Inflation had a positive effect on stock prices, while interest rate and exchange rate changes negatively affected stock prices across all three categories.

2.3 Interest rate and industrial good sector index

Dwijaya (2024) determined the impact of interest rate hikes on sectoral index stock prices on the Indonesia Stock Exchange; in addition, the study predicted the volatility of sectoral indices using monthly data for the period 2021-2024. Simple correlation to determine the impact of interest rates on sectoral index stock prices and volatility methods using ARIMA, ARCH, and GARCH to determine the best model for analysis. The result showed that an increase in interest rates has a significant positive impact on the finance banking sector, energy mineral sector, and utility sector. It has a negative impact on the industry sector and no significant impact on the distribution sector.

Sukmawati and Haryono (2021) analyzed the cointegration between interest rate, the Dow Jones Industrial Average, and Indonesia's IHSG using monthly data from 2015–2019. Applying ADF, Johansen cointegration, and ECM techniques, they found no long-run cointegration between the DJIA and IHSG, suggesting that investors responded more to global and domestic sentiment than to U.S. market movements. The exchange rate also showed no long-run relationship with the IHSG, as their movements were not consistently aligned. Likewise, interest rates were not cointegrated with the IHSG because most IDX sectors were more influenced by external sentiment than domestic interest rate changes.

Hassan et al (2019) examined the relationship between Turkish stock market activities by identifying variables that affect particularly the Industrial Index of the market using monthly data for the period January 2003 to December 2013. The study used Ordinary Least Squares regression to analyze the series. A Multivariate Regression Model computed on Standard OLS Formula has been used to estimate the relationship. Based on regression coefficient, it was found that Inflation, Exchange rate, Money supply and Interest rate all had negative influence on BIST-KYD index.

Banda et al (2019) examined the relationship between macroeconomic variables (aggregate economic output, inflation, interest rates and exchange rates) and industrial shares in developing countries. The Industrial Index (INDI 25) on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE) was analyzed using data from 1995 to 2017. The results showed that inflation has a significant positive relationship with stock prices. However, a negative relationship was found between interest rates and stock prices. In the period, exchange rates had a positive effect on industrial shares, but no relationship was identified between industrial shares and the gross domestic product (GDP).

Amassoma and Adeleke (2018) analyzed the causal relationship between interest rate and stock market performance using a VECM-based Granger causality test on annual time series data from 1975 to 2016. The rationale for the study emanated from the unpredictable behavior of the Nigerian stock exchange from the outset of the global financial economic crisis from 2007/8 till date couple to the increasingly high key policy rates like interest rate by the CBN that has refused to drop. The results revealed that the interest rate exerted a negative but statistically insignificant relation to stock market

performance in the long run. In addition, Granger causality test result noted that there was no causality between interest rate and stock market performance.

Duy (2017) investigated the factors that affect the price of the shares of industrial companies listed on the Stock Exchange in Ho Chi Minh City (HOSE). The data used in the study are collected according to the date of publication unified consumer price index of the Central Statistical Office (on the 24th of the last month of the quarter) from 2012 to 2015. Using regression analysis showed that EPS and exchange rate (USD / VND) and interest rate correlated to the profitability ratio of the shares the price of gold and the rate of inflation measured by the consumer price index (CPI) has negative correlation to rate profitability of the shares.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Asset pricing models

The Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT), introduced by Ross (1976), provides a multi-factor alternative to the single-factor CAPM. Instead of relying solely on market risk, APT proposes that asset returns are driven by several macroeconomic factors, each with its own sensitivity coefficient. When prices deviate from fair value, arbitrage forces them back into equilibrium, implying that returns including those of sector-specific stocks are shaped by both market-wide movements and macroeconomic conditions (Ouma & Muriu, 2014).

A key advantage of APT is its flexibility: unlike CAPM, it does not restrict the model to one systematic factor. Analysts can select relevant variables such as interest rates, inflation, or exchange rates to better explain asset price behavior (Drake & Fabozzi, 2012). This makes APT particularly useful for examining how different sectors respond to changing economic environments.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts *ex post facto* research design. The independent variables are interest rate and exchange rate, while the dependent variables are industrial goods sector index. It employs monthly secondary data which were sourced from the various official publications of the Nigerian Exchange Group and National Bureau of Statistics for the period between 2012 and 2025. VECM was used for data analysis. VECM was used for estimating both short-term and long-term effects of one time series on another. The VECM is stated below;

$$\Delta \text{ININDEX}_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{g=1}^{k-1} \beta_g \Delta \text{ININDEX}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \partial_i \Delta \text{EXCR}_{t-i} + \sum_{h=1}^{k-1} \phi_h \Delta \text{INTR}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \partial_i \Delta \text{INFR}_{t-i} + \lambda_1 \text{ECT}_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where;

ININDEX = Industrial Goods Sector Index

EXCR = Exchange Rate

INTR = Interest Rate

INFR = Inflation Rate

t = Periods covered by the study

ECT_{t-1} = the error correction which is the lagged value of the residuals obtained from the co-integrating regression of the dependent variable on the regressors

Δ = denotes the first difference operator,

σ is the drift component,

α = Intercept of the regression,

ε_t = Residuals

λ = Speed of adjustment parameter with a negative sign

$K-1$ = the lag length

γ_i = Short run dynamic coefficients of the model's adjustment to long run equilibrium

α = The constant

$\beta_g, \phi_h, \vartheta_i$ = short-run dynamic coefficients of the model's adjustment of long-run equilibrium.

Data analysis and results

Table 1 Summary of basic descriptive statistics

	EXCH	INFL	INTR	ININDEX
Mean	437.8946	15.76667	15.16071	2231.039
Median	305.6450	14.28000	13.50000	2052.135
Maximum	1674.640	34.80000	27.50000	5955.840
Minimum	130.8100	7.700000	11.00000	1001.110
Std. Dev.	451.9646	6.900104	5.002940	1040.006
Skewness	1.815445	1.132375	1.672354	1.534494
Kurtosis	4.731889	3.708479	4.360292	5.314774
Observations	168	168	168	168

Source: Extracted from EViews Output

The descriptive statistics summarize 168 monthly observations for six key variables. The mean values provide a measure of central tendency over the sample period. The average exchange rate (EXCH) was approximately ₦438/\$1, while the average inflation rate (INFL) was 15.77% and the average monetary policy rate (INTR) was 15.16% and 2,231.04 points for the Industrial Goods Index (ININDEX).

The standard deviation reveals significant volatility in all series, with the exchange rate (EXCH) exhibiting the highest absolute dispersion (Std. Dev. 452). This indicates intense fluctuation in the Naira's value, consistent with periods of devaluation and forex market instability. Inflation (INFL) also shows considerable variability (Std. Dev. 6.9), reflecting periods of relative price stability and episodes of sharp price surges while Industrial Goods Index (Std. Dev. 1040) display wide dispersions, especially the pointing to substantial swings in market valuation over the period. The high standard deviations relative to the means underscore the turbulent economic environment captured in the data.

The range between maximum and minimum values highlights dramatic extremes. The exchange rate swung from ₦130.8/\$1 to ₦1,674.64/\$1, capturing the profound transition from a managed regime to a floated and heavily depreciated Naira. Inflation ranged from a low of 7.7% to a high of 34.8%, illustrating intervals of single-digit inflation and episodes of severe inflationary pressure. The Interest Rate moved from 11% to 27.5%, reflecting the Central Bank aggressive response to macroeconomic shocks. Similarly, an

Industrial Goods Index reached record highs multiples of their minimums, demonstrating both bear and bull market phases within the period.

Correlation matrix

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for Variables

Correlation Probability	EXCH	INFL	INTR	ININDEX
EXCH	1.000000 -----			
INFL	0.668691 0.0000	1.000000 -----		
INTR	0.767649 0.0000	0.750770 0.0000	1.000000 -----	
ININDEX	0.607716 0.0000	0.585283 0.0000	0.601011 0.0000	1.000000 -----

Source: Output from E-views 12, 2026.

The correlation matrix shows significant positive relationships between the macroeconomic variables and the Industrial Goods Index (ININDEX), with all coefficients significant at the 5% level (p = 0.0000). The exchange rate exhibits a positive correlation with the Industrial Goods Index, suggesting that Naira depreciation is associated with higher index values. Interest rate also shows a positive relationship with the index, while inflation records a moderate positive correlation with the Industrial Goods Index (0.585).

Specifically, the correlation between the exchange rate (EXCH) and the interest rate (INTR) is 0.768, while the correlation between inflation (INFL) and the interest rate is 0.751. The correlation between exchange rate and inflation is 0.669. Although the macroeconomic variables are correlated with one another, none of the pairwise correlations exceed the 0.80 threshold, indicating the absence of severe multicollinearity. This implies that the variables maintain sufficient independent variation to identify their individual effects on the Industrial Goods Index.

Unit Root Test

Table 3: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

Variables	AT LEVEL			AT FIRST DIFFERENCE				
	ADF Test Statistic	Critical Value @ 5%	P-Value	ADF Test Statistic	Critical Value @ 5%	P-Value	Max Lag	Order of Integration
EXCH	-0.8734	-2.8794	0.7945	-2.9823	-2.8794	0.0397	8	1(I)
INFL	-1.8777	-2.8792	0.3422	-9.4599	-2.8788	0.0000	8	1(1)
INTR	0.2217	-2.8792	0.9732	-4.6329	-2.8792	0.0002	8	1(1)
ININDEX	-0.1659	-2.8788	0.9390	-15.498	-2.8788	0.0000	8	1(1)

Source: Eview 12 Output, 2026.

According to the result of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test conducted to assess the stationarity properties of the variables at both levels and first differences. At levels, all variables were found to be non-stationary. The ADF statistics (e.g., EXCH: -0.8734; INTR: 0.2217) were greater than the 5% critical values, with corresponding p-values exceeding 0.05 (ranging from 0.3422 to 0.9732). This indicates a failure to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root, confirming that the series contain stochastic trends.

However, after first differencing, all variables achieved stationarity. The ADF statistics became significantly more negative (e.g., EXCH: -2.9823; INFL: -9.4599; INTR: -4.6329), with p-values below the 0.05 threshold (0.0397 for EXCH and 0.0000 for others). This allows for the rejection of the unit root null. Consequently, all variables are integrated of order one, I (1). This uniform order of integration satisfies a key condition for conducting cointegration analysis, which will examine long-run equilibrium relationships among the variables.

Johansen Co-Integration Test

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: ININDEX EXCH INFL INTR

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 4

Table 4

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.122474	50.67470	47.85613	0.0265
At most 1 *	0.111313	29.90156	29.79707	0.0486
At most 2	0.067645	11.13792	15.49471	0.2032
At most 3	8.13E-06	0.001293	3.841466	0.9704

Source: Eview 12 Output, 2026.

The Johansen co-integration test is applied here to investigate the presence of long-run equilibrium relationships among four variables: ININDEX, EXCH, INFL, and INTR., using the Trace statistic with lags 1 to 4. The results confirm the presence of cointegration. The "None" hypothesis (no cointegration) is rejected, as the Trace statistic of 50.67 exceeds the 5% critical value of 47.86 ($p = 0.0265 < 0.05$), indicating at least one long-run relationship. Furthermore, the "At most 1" hypothesis is also rejected (Trace = 29.90 > 29.80; $p = 0.0486 < 0.05$), confirming at least two cointegrating equations. However, the "At most 2" hypothesis cannot be rejected (Trace = 11.14 < 15.49; $p = 0.2032 > 0.05$). The test therefore concludes that two cointegrating equations exist among the variables. This implies that the four series are bound together in a stable system governed by two distinct long-run equilibrium paths.

Table 5: Long Run VECM Result
Dependent Variable: ININDEX

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	p-value
EXCH(-1)	-1.605556	(1.44203)	[-1.11340]	.267
INFL(-1)	185.8340	(40.0942)	[4.63493]	.001
INTR(-1)	-125.7275	(129.036)	[-0.97436]	.331
Constant	-2556.173			

Source: Eview 12 Output, 2026.

The long-run equilibrium relationship between the Industrial Goods Sector Index (ININDEX) and macroeconomic variables (exchange rate, inflation, interest rate) is presented below, normalized on ININDEX with a constant of -2556.173.

Inflation Rate (INFL) exhibits a strong positive and highly significant coefficient of 185.8340 ($p < 0.001$). A one-percentage-point increase in inflation is associated with a long-run increase of approximately 185.83 units in the industrial goods index. This positive relationship likely reflects the tangible asset holdings of industrial firms' factories, equipment, and inventory whose replacement values rise during inflationary periods. Additionally, pricing power may enable these firms to pass on higher costs, protecting or enhancing profit margins.

Exchange Rate (EXCH) shows a negative coefficient of -1.605556 but is not statistically significant ($p = 0.267$). This suggests no discernible long-run effect of exchange rate movements on the sector. The insignificance may stem from heterogeneous firm-level exposures: some firms benefit from currency depreciation through export competitiveness, while others face higher costs for imported inputs. These opposing effects may cancel out at the aggregate level, or firms may have developed effective hedging strategies.

Interest Rate (INTR) also lacks statistical significance, with a coefficient of -125.7275 ($p = 0.331$). Although the negative direction aligns with theory higher capital costs potentially compressing valuations the insignificance may reflect reliance on retained earnings rather than bank financing among industrial firms, or indirect capture of interest rate effects through correlated variables like inflation.

Table 6: Short Run VECM Result
Dependent Variable: ININDEX

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	p-value
ECM (-1)	-0.613847	(0.12551)	[-4.89082]	0 .001
D(EXCH(-1))	0.658793	(0.60153)	[1.09520]	0.275
D(INFL(-1))	-21.83814	(23.8612)	[-0.91521]	0.361
D(INTR(-1))	-96.57075	(61.5030)	[-1.57018]	0.118
Constant	37.02139	(24.7219)	[1.49752]	0.136
Model Fit Statistics				Value
R ²				0.559
Adjusted R ²				0 .430
F-statistic				7.019
p-value (F-statistic)				0.001

Source: EViews 12 Output, 2026.

The short-run VECM results capture the month-to-month response of the Industrial Goods Sector Index to macroeconomic changes while maintaining long-run equilibrium. The model shows moderate explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.559$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.430$) and is statistically significant ($F = 7.019$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the included variables meaningfully explain short-run variations.

The error correction term ECM (-1) is -0.6138 and significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.001$), confirming a long-run equilibrium relationship. This implies that about 61% of any disequilibrium from the previous period is corrected within a month, indicating a strong adjustment toward long-run stability.

However, none of the short-run coefficients of the macroeconomic variables are statistically significant. Exchange rate shows a positive but insignificant effect, while inflation and interest rate have negative but insignificant effects. This suggests that short-term movements in the Industrial Goods Sector Index are not strongly driven by immediate changes in these macroeconomic variables but rather by long-run equilibrium dynamics.

Post Estimation Diagnostics Tests

Table 7: Post Estimation Diagnostics Tests

Test	P-Value
Heteroskedasticity Test	0.2114
Serial Correlation LM Test	0.3198
Normality Test	0.8126

Source: Author's Computation from EViews 12 Results, 2026.

The result as presented in the above table revealed that there were no evidences of heteroskedasticity, serial correlation, and the data are normally distributed in the estimated VECM model with *p-values* of 0.2114, 0.3198 and 0.8126 respectively. They were all found to be greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The Vector Error Correction Model reveals a complex interplay between the banking sector index and its macroeconomic determinants, with findings that both align with and contradict various studies. The model confirms the existence of a significant long-run equilibrium relationship, while the short-run dynamics highlight the sector's adaptive nature.

The VECM results show that the exchange rate does not have a statistically significant effect on the Nigerian industrial goods sector index in either the long run or the short run. In the long run, the exchange rate coefficient was negative but insignificant ($p = 0.267$), suggesting that currency depreciation does not independently influence sector performance. Similarly, the short-run coefficient was positive but also insignificant ($p = 0.275$), indicating that short-term exchange rate fluctuations do not meaningfully affect the sector. These findings imply that exchange rate movements are not a primary driver of industrial goods sector performance in Nigeria. Although currency depreciation may theoretically increase production costs through higher prices of imported machinery and raw materials, the effect appears weak at the aggregate sector level.

This result is consistent with several empirical studies, including those by Ajibogun et al. (2025), Kushwah and Negi (2024) which also found insignificant short-run exchange rate effects on industrial output and sector indices. However, other studies such as Iheanacho and Akpan reported significant exchange rate impacts, highlighting that sector responses may vary across countries and industries. From a theoretical perspective, the findings suggest that exchange rates may not be a systematically priced risk factor for industrial goods sector returns, contrary to the expectations of Arbitrage Pricing Theory. The results may also reflect the ability of firms to absorb exchange rate shocks through operational adjustments or pricing strategies.

The results further reveal a clear distinction between the long-run and short-run effects of inflation. In the long run, inflation has a strong positive and statistically significant effect on the industrial goods sector index ($p < 0.001$). This suggests that sustained increases in inflation are associated with improvements in the sector's performance.

In contrast, the short-run effect of inflation was negative but statistically insignificant, indicating that short-term fluctuations in inflation do not immediately affect sector performance. This implies that industrial firms adjust gradually to inflation through pricing strategies, asset revaluation, and operational adjustments. These findings align with studies such as Suriani et al (2024), and Gibet (2016), which also reported positive relationships between inflation and industrial sector performance. However, other studies, including Odondo (2021), found negative effects of inflation on manufacturing output, suggesting that inflation effects vary across economies and sectors. The results support the predictions of Arbitrage Pricing Theory, which identifies inflation as a key macroeconomic risk factor influencing asset returns. The positive long-run relationship may reflect the ability of industrial firms to pass rising costs to consumers and benefit from the nominal appreciation of assets during inflationary periods.

The VECM results indicate that interest rates do not significantly influence the industrial goods sector index in either the long run or the short run. The long-run coefficient was negative but statistically insignificant ($p = 0.331$), while the short-run coefficient was also negative and close to significance ($p = 0.118$). The negative direction of the coefficients suggests that higher interest rates could potentially reduce sector performance by increasing borrowing costs and discouraging investment. However, the lack of statistical significance indicates that interest rates are not a dominant factor affecting industrial goods sector performance in Nigeria. These findings are consistent with studies such as Amassoma & Adeleke (2018), and Sukmawati & Haryono (2021) which also reported insignificant relationships between interest rates and stock market performance. Nevertheless, other studies in emerging markets have found significant negative effects, indicating that the sensitivity of industrial sectors to interest rates may vary across countries. The results suggest that Nigerian industrial firms may rely less on interest-sensitive financing or may have developed strategies that reduce their exposure to interest rate fluctuations.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study underscores the heterogeneous and adaptive nature of the Nigerian stock market, particularly within the industrial goods sector, and validates the relevance of multi-factor frameworks such as the Arbitrage Pricing Theory in explaining sectorial stock behavior. Specifically, the results reveal that inflation is the only macroeconomic

variable with a statistically significant long-run effect on the industrial goods sector index. Its positive relationship suggests that industrial firms are able to adjust to persistent price increases through asset revaluation and cost pass-through mechanisms. In contrast, exchange rate and interest rate were found to be statistically insignificant in both the long run and short run, implying that their independent effects on the sector are limited at the aggregate level. This may reflect offsetting firm-level exposures, adaptive strategies, or structural characteristics of the sector. In the short run, none of the macroeconomic variables significantly influenced the index, highlighting that sector performance is largely driven by long-run adjustments rather than immediate macroeconomic shocks.

The significant and negative error correction term further confirms a strong speed of adjustment, with approximately 61% of disequilibrium corrected within a month. Based on the findings, the study recommends that, policymakers should prioritize effective inflation management strategies to maintain macroeconomic stability. Monetary authorities should adopt a balanced approach to interest rate adjustments, as aggressive tightening may not significantly benefit the industrial sector but could constrain broader economic growth. Government should provide targeted support (e.g., tax incentives, subsidies, or infrastructure improvements) to industrial firms to cushion the indirect effects of exchange rate volatility.

Investors should pay closer attention to inflation trends when making long-term investment decisions in the industrial goods sector. Given the weak short-run effects of macroeconomic variables, investors should adopt a long-term investment horizon rather than relying on short-term macroeconomic signals. Portfolio diversification across sectors is advisable, as different sectors respond differently to macroeconomic shocks. Firms should strengthen inflation-hedging strategies, including efficient pricing mechanisms and cost management practices. There is a need to reduce reliance on imported inputs by promoting local sourcing and backward integration, which can mitigate exposure to exchange rate fluctuations. Companies should explore alternative financing options (e.g., equity financing, retained earnings) to minimize sensitivity to interest rate movements.

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